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Cultivating Resilience in Health:
Towards Unified Equitable Strategies for
Climate Adaptation and Mitigation in Africa

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ABSTRACT eBOOK

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507 TRACK E: One Health Approach to Mitigating Zoonotic Spillover Risks in Cambodia

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Background, rationale, and objectives: This research examines the complex interplay of human, animal, and environmental factors in the emergence of zoonotic diseases. Specifically, it focuses on the practices of harvesting bat guano in caves in Cambodia, a context rife with potential for disease spillover. By adopting a One Health perspective, this study explores the risks associated with bat-human interaction and the implications for public health.

Methods: Through ethnographic fieldwork and participatory action research, we explored the socio-ecological conditions that influence disease transmission. Our findings highlight the vulnerabilities of bat guano

harvesters to respiratory and skin ailments, underscoring the occupational hazards of this livelihood. We argue that these health risks are inextricably linked to broader ecological and socio-economic factors.

Results: To address these challenges, we collaborated with local communities to co-design and implement biosafety and hygiene interventions aimed at reducing spillover risks. Our approach emphasizes the importance of community empowerment and knowledge sharing. By integrating local perspectives and practices into our interventions, we sought to develop sustainable solutions that are culturally appropriate and contextually relevant.

Conclusion/Implications: This study contributes to the growing body of literature on zoonotic disease prevention by demonstrating the efficacy of community-based approaches. Our findings underscore the need for interdisciplinary research and policy development to address the complex challenges posed by emerging infectious diseases. By fostering collaboration between human and animal health sectors, we can build more resilient and equitable health systems.

Keywords: One Health, zoonotic diseases, bat guano harvesting, Cambodia, community engagement, health inequalities, environmental health.

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